

Verifying Z3 SAT Proofs with the Interactive Theorems Prover Coq/Rocq and Agda

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Ensuring the correctness of safety-critical systems, such as railway control systems, remains paramount. To achieve this, machine-assisted theorem proving is increasingly adopted in the railway domain. Tools like Z3 [17] are used to formally verify that these systems meet stringent safety standards. For example, our group has applied such techniques in the verification of geographic scheme data and ladder logic interlockings [2, 11]. These approaches help identify design flaws early, reducing the risk and cost associated with later-stage testing and certification. However, any of these solvers may have flaws or implement optimisations that produce incorrect results. To increase trust, proof checking offers an independent check of the Z3 output. We are developing a verified SAT proof checker for Z3 using its new Reverse Unit Propagation (RUP) format. We have also incorporated a checking procedure for the Tseitin Transformation to achieve propositional formulae in conjunctive normal form (CNF) [26]. The new RUP proof format was introduced to the Z3 theorem prover in September 2022, replacing resolution [7]. Proof checking for other proof formats for SAT and SMT solving has been performed in, e.g., [8, 10, 9, 12, 41, 15, 43, 21, 13, 27, 41, 42, 36, 25, 16, 18, 1, 20, 30, 3, 5, 4, 19, 31, 33, 35, 6].

The notion of a RUP proof was introduced by van Gelder [23, 22] in 2008. It addresses the issue that resolution proofs can be too lengthy to store feasibly while still allowing efficient checking. The underlying concept is proof verification by Goldberg and Novikov [24], where unit propagation checks unsatisfiability without storing full resolution proofs. Van Gelder refined this into RUP, requiring each derived clause to cause a contradiction when added, making proofs more compact and efficient. RUP takes logical statements written in CNF, where each clause is a disjunction of literals $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$. Negation of a literal x_i simply switches from x_i to $\neg x_i$, or vice versa. A formula is a conjunction of clauses. Z3 deals with formulae not in CNF by translating them using the Tseitin transformation [40, 34, 29].

A RUP inference of a clause $C = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ from assumptions (clauses) Γ is correct, if from $\Gamma' := \Gamma, \{\neg x_1\}, \dots, \{\neg x_n\}$ we can derive the empty clause $\{\}$ using only unit-clause propagation. A RUP proof from an initial clause set Γ_0 is a sequence of clauses C_i , for $i \geq 1$, such that for all i C_i is a RUP inference from Γ_{i-1} , where $\Gamma_j = \Gamma_{j-1} \cup \{C_j\}$, for $j \geq 1$. If some C_j is the empty clause $\{\}$, the sequence is a RUP refutation [23]. Checking a RUP inference is done as follows: Divide Γ' into non-unit clauses Γ_{nonunit} (clauses of length ≥ 2) and unit clauses Γ_{unit} (clauses of length 1). If an empty clause is found, then we have derived falsity, and Γ was already unsatisfiable. While $\Gamma_{\text{unit}} \neq \emptyset$, we repeatedly select a unit clause x from Γ_{unit} , remove it, and apply unit resolution with all clauses in $\Gamma_{\text{unit}} \cup \Gamma_{\text{nonunit}}$. If c contains x , then it is implied by $\{x\}$ and is therefore removed. Otherwise, if c contains $\neg x$, then a unit resolution of c with

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$\{x\}$ derives $c' := c \setminus \{\neg x\}$. We replace c by c' ; if it has length ≥ 2 , it will be in Γ_{nunit} , and if it has length 1, in Γ_{unit} . If it has length 0, then we have derived $\{\}$, so the RUP inference is verified, and we exit the loop. If c does not contain x or $\neg x$, it is kept. Once we have applied unit resolution with $\{x\}$ to all the clauses in $\Gamma_{\text{unit}} \cup \Gamma_{\text{nunit}}$, we repeat the process. After each step, the literal x and its negation do not occur anymore in $\Gamma_{\text{unit}} \cup \Gamma_{\text{nunit}}$, and no new literals have been created, so eventually the loop terminates because Γ_{unit} is empty. If we have not derived $\{\}$ by then, then $\{\}$ is not derivable by unit clause propagation, thus the verification of the RUP inference fails. At each step, all formulae in $\Gamma_{\text{unit}} \cup \Gamma_{\text{nunit}}$ are derivable from Γ using unit clause resolution; therefore, they are entailed. If the procedure succeeds, then Γ' entails falsity and is therefore unsatisfiable. Thus, by classical logic (we have tertium non datur for the Boolean variables) it follows that Γ entails $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$.

We have formalised our Z3 SAT proof-checker in Rocq [37], previously known as Coq [14], and developed a procedure to validate Z3-generated proofs using the Reverse Unit Propagation (RUP) format [23, 22, 24]. In RUP, each inference step shows that a clause is logically entailed by the assumptions, by demonstrating that its negation leads to a contradiction through unit propagation. The proof concludes when falsity is derived, confirming unsatisfiability. In addition to clause-level validation, we have developed a TreeProof-level version of the checker, which constructs structured resolution traces that mirror the logical steps taken during unit propagation. These traces, called TreeProofs, represent the derivation of clauses from assumptions using a tree-like structure, where each node corresponds to either an assumption or a unit resolution step. This approach provides a structural view of the unit resolution process, enhancing confidence in the correctness of each inference. A TreeProof is valid if all assumptions referenced are within bounds and each resolution step is logically sound - particularly when resolving with unit clauses. To ensure soundness, we proved that if the checker returns true, then the assumptions logically entail the derived clause. By formalising and verifying both clause-level and TreeProof-level checking, we ensure that Z3's proofs can be trusted independently of the solver's internal mechanisms - an essential requirement for safety-critical applications.

Functions to check RUP inferences can be extracted from Rocq [37] into executable code using Rocq's extraction mechanism [32], typically to OCaml or Haskell. A parser for Z3 proof logs for ladder logic interlockings has also been developed. Extraction to other languages is possible, for example, C using the Codegen package [38]. Extraction to C supports basic types like numbers and lists, but complex types need extra handling or may not be supported. This is problematic for dependent types or higher-order functions lacking C equivalents.

Currently, proofs of correctness for RUP rely on generating all intermediate resolution proofs for each RUP inference. In fact, generating these proofs may be desirable when working with critical systems. Although having a proof that the checker is correct provides a high level of trust, there remains a remote possibility that an inconsistency in Rocq was used. Genuine bugs are occasionally detected in theorem provers. Therefore, having independently verifiable proof logs would allow for an even higher level of trust. The additional generated intermediate resolution proofs make it easier and therefore more trustworthy to verify the RUP proofs.

To support Z3 SAT proof logs, we extended our checker to validate Tseitin Transformations to convert non-CNF formulas for RUP whilst preserving satisfiability by introducing tautological clauses. Our prototype, implemented in Agda [39], matches these clauses against known patterns and formally proves their correctness [28]. This complements our verified RUP checker, forming a complete proof checker for propositional logic. This is now being replicated in OCaml for integration with the RUP Checker, with formal proofs in Rocq, ensuring each rule preserves satisfiability. By continuing to verify new rules in this way, we expand the checker's coverage while maintaining trustworthiness - essential for industrial applications.

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